

Regioselective synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles catalyzed by cooperative s-block bimetallics

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SUMMARY

While 1,4-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles can be readily prepared by copper(I) alkyne/azide cycloaddition, the methods available to access the alternative 1,5-disubstituted isomers have been significantly less well developed. Exploiting chemical cooperativity, here we report the first examples of s-block bimetallic catalysis using a sodium magnesiate precatalyst as an efficient and versatile new method to synthesize 1,5-disubstituted triazoles via azide/alkyne ligation. Showing an excellent substrate scope and selectivity under mild reaction conditions, this bimetallic approach has also been successfully applied to access symmetrical and non-symmetrical di-triazoles. Mechanistic insights on how the Na/Mg cooperative partnership is established are also provided, supporting a stepwise process where initial deprotonation of the alkyne renders a highly nucleophilic tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate to which the azide can coordinate, facilitating its insertion into an Mg-C bond and subsequent cyclization, which is favored by p-coordination of Na to the alkyne C≡C triple bond.

INTRODUCTION

Among *N*-heterocyclic molecules, 1,2,3-triazoles represent one of the most synthetically relevant scaffolds, present in a myriad of pharmaceuticals and with numerous applications in drug discovery¹⁻³ and materials science.^{4,5} Copper-catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of an azide with a terminal alkyne (CuAAC) constitutes a particularly versatile method to access *N*-heterocyclic motifs.^{6,7} Key for the success of this approach is its excellent functional group tolerance, mild reaction conditions, and exquisite control of the regioselectivity, granting access exclusively to 1,4-disubstituted triazoles.⁸⁻¹⁰

In contrast, the methods to selectively synthesize 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles have been significantly underdeveloped,¹¹⁻¹⁷ and therefore the potential applications of these molecules in drug discovery and materials chemistry still remain underexplored when compared with those of the more studied 1,4-disubstituted systems that are easily accessed by CuAAC reactions.¹⁸⁻²⁰ A landmark discovery in this field was the use of Ru(II) catalysis reported by Zhang et al. in 2005,¹³ which furnishes both 1,4- and 1,5-regioisomers but for which the selectivity can be finely tuned by modifying the supporting ligands on Ru to furnish the relevant 1,5-disubstituted triazoles. In the search for catalytic alternatives that do not require the use of noble transition metals, Zhou and coworkers have noted that rare-earth metal amides [Ln{N(SiMe₃)₂}]₃ can be used as precatalysts in the cycloaddition of terminal alkynes and azides to give 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles, although long reaction times

and additives need to be employed.¹⁶ Fokin has also extended the methodology to a transition-metal-free, base-catalyzed approach using aqueous NMe₄OH or KO^tBu in DMSO at room temperature, but this is limited mainly to activated aryl-acetylenes and aryl-azides.¹⁴ While these reactions seem to operate by initial deprotonation of the terminal alkyne, the constitution of the intermediates involved in these catalytic processes have not been determined.

s-Block organometallics have also shown some promise to access 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles, although they need to be employed under controlled stoichiometric conditions.^{11,12} These methods involve the *in situ* formation of s-block (lithium, sodium, and magnesium) acetylides; however, the high reactivity and polarity of these systems greatly compromises substrate scope and necessitates the use of low temperatures.²¹ Greaney has addressed some of these limitations by employing ZnEt₂ as a precursor to generate the relevant zinc acetylides that undergo a subsequent [3 + 2] cycloaddition reaction with organic azides, showing a greater functional group tolerance.¹⁵

While, to date, these s-/p-block organometallic approaches have not yet been up-graded to catalytic regimes, over the past decade, main-group metal catalysis has become a consolidated field toward the aspiration of sustainable synthesis.^{22–25} In parallel to these catalytic studies, another evolving area of s-block organometallic chemistry has been the synthesis and reactivity of mixed-metal reagents for chemical cooperativity. Combining a group 1 metal with a less electropositive s- or p-block metal partner such as Mg, Zn, or Al, these systems have demonstrated unique reactivity and improved selectivity that cannot be matched by their single metal components.^{26,27} Furthermore, recently some of these stoichiometric successes have been applied to catalytic regimes, providing some of the first examples of main-group metal cooperative catalysis.^{28,29}

Breaking new ground in this field, here we report the first catalytic applications of sodium magnesiates to promote the regioselective synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted-1,2,3-triazoles. Combining kinetic studies with the isolation of key organometallic intermediates, mechanistic insights have been gained that illustrate how chemical cooperation operates in these reactions by elaborating the key role played by each metal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have previously demonstrated the use of alkali-metal magnesiates to catalyze atom-economical transformations, such as the intramolecular hydroalkoxylation of alkynols³⁰ and the intermolecular hydroamination of isocyanates,³¹ carbodiimides,³² and internal alkynes.³³ These studies have revealed that the formation of anionically activated “ate” intermediates is a crucial factor in order to enhance the nucleophilic power of the catalyst. Furthermore, for less activated unsaturated substrates such as alkynes, the alkali-metal facilitates the hydroamination (or hydroalkoxylation) process by acting as a “built-in” Lewis acid to which the substrate can coordinate. To this end, we were interested in investigating these bimetallic catalysts toward enabling the regioselective ligation of terminal alkynes with organic azides.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopic monitoring of a THF-d₈ solution of phenylacetylene (1a) and benzylazide (2a) with 5 mol % NaMg(CH₂SiMe₃)₃³⁴ gave quantitative formation of the 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole (3aa) after 6 h at 65°C. Encouraged by these findings, we next tried higher-order

Table 1. Reaction optimization for the regioselective synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles

Entry	Catalyst	Loading (mol %)	Time (hours)	Yield (%) ^a
1	NaMg(CH ₂ SiMe ₃) ₃	5	6	>99
2	(TMEDA) ₂ Na ₂ Mg(CH ₂ SiMe ₃) ₄	5	0.75	>99
3	No catalyst	–	48	traces ^b
4	NaCH ₂ SiMe ₃	5	48	10 ^c
5	Mg(CH ₂ SiMe ₃) ₂	5	6	>99
6	LiCH ₂ SiMe ₃	5	48	29
7	KO ^t Bu	5	2	traces ^d
8	(PMDETA) ₂ K ₂ Mg(CH ₂ SiMe ₃) ₄	5	2–24 ^e	64
9	(TMEDA) ₂ Na ₂ Mg(CH ₂ SiMe ₃) ₄ + 15-crown-5 ^f	5	2	10

^aYields determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopic data against an internal standard (10 mol % ferrocene).

^b1:1 ratio of 1,5- and 1,4-regioisomers.

^c4:1 ratio of 1,5- and 1,4-regioisomers, alongside other unidentified side products.

^dImmediate decomposition of 2a.

^eMaximum yield of 64% obtained after 2 hours of heating, with no further conversion after extended heating.

^f10 mol % 15-crown-5.

(2:1, Na:Mg stoichiometric ratio) sodium magnesiate (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄,³⁵ (TMEDA = *N,N,N',N'*-tetramethylethylenediamine) for which quantitative conversion to the 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole 3aa was achieved after just 45 min (Table 1, entry 2). Significantly, when the reaction is performed in the absence of a catalyst, only trace quantities of a mixture of 1,4- and 1,5-regioisomers were observed after 48 h of heating (Table 1, entry 3). This result is consistent with the high kinetic barrier and lack of selectivity that has been reported for the uncatalyzed process.³⁶ Demonstrating the superior catalytic power of bimetallic (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄ over its individual monometallic constituents, only traces of 3aa were observed when using 5 mol % Na(CH₂SiMe₃)₃³⁷ (Table 1, entry 4), while complete conversion was reached with Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₂, albeit with 6 h of heating (Table 1, entry 5). Using other group 1 metal basic reagents led to the formation of 3aa in significantly lower yields. Thus, Li(CH₂SiMe₃)₃ furnished 3aa in a modest 29% after 48 h (Table 1, entry 6), whereas KO^tBu led to the violent decomposition of azide 2a at room temperature, affording only traces of 3aa. Replacing Na by K, employing heavier, higher-order potassium magnesiate (PMDETA)₂K₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄³⁵ evidenced a significant alkali-metal effect, affording 3aa in a reduced 64% yield even after extended heating (Table 1, entry 8). In an attempt to glean some information into the role of sodium in this transformation, the reaction with (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄ was carried out in the presence of an additional 10 mol % (two equivalents) of 15-crown-5. Since this macrocyclic polydentate donor has a high sequestering affinity for sodium cations, we pondered that in its presence we might saturate the coordination of the alkali-metal, thereby preventing access of the substrate and slowing down the reaction. The outcome seemed to verify this thinking since under these conditions, only trace conversion to the 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole is observed (Table 1, entry 9), highlighting the crucial role of a coordinatively accessible alkali-metal for this catalytic transformation.

Figure 1. Reaction scope using $(\text{TMEDA})_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_4$ precatalyst

Reactions were carried out in 2 mL of THF using 1.2 mmol of alkyne, 1 mmol of azide, and 0.05 mmol of precatalyst. Yields refer to isolated yields of analytically pure products (> 95% purity determined by NMR spectroscopy or GC analysis).

^a81% spectroscopic yield.

Using 5 mol % of the higher-order sodium magnesiate precatalyst, $(\text{TMEDA})_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_4$, the scope of the reaction was investigated using a range of aromatic and aliphatic alkynes and azides (Figure 1). This methodology allowed the formation of 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles in good to excellent yields (up to 99%) with short reaction times (typically 0.5 to 3 h), which contrasts with other methods, such as those using rare-earth metal precatalysts, that require prolonged heating for up to 24 h.¹⁶ Using benzylazide (2a), the corresponding triazoles (3ba and 3ca) were obtained in good yields (71% and 93%, respectively) when treated with different aryl-alkynes (1a–c). Shorter reaction times were required using phenylazide (2b) and (hetero) aromatic and aliphatic alkynes (1a–e), to give the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles (3ab, 3bb, 3db, 3cb, and 3eb) in good to excellent yields (96%, 86%, 71%, 92%, and 92%, respectively), contrasting with the sluggish reactivity noted for aliphatic alkynes and azides when using ammonium salts or KO^tBu .¹⁴

The same methodology is extendable to substituted aryl-azides bearing electron-donating groups. 1-Azido-2-methoxybenzene (2c) reacted smoothly with (hetero)

aromatic and aliphatic alkynes (1a, 1f, and 1c) to give the corresponding triazoles (3ac, 3fc, and 3cc) in high yields (99%, 89%, and 99%, respectively) after just 30 min of heating. The electron-rich and sterically demanding 2-azido-1,3-dimethylbenzene (2d) was also found to be a compatible reaction partner with a range of alkynes (1a, 1b, 1d, 1f, and 1g) to again give the target triazoles (3ad, 3bd, 3dd, 3fd, and 3gd) in good to excellent yields (92%, 93%, 76%, 87%, and 89%, respectively) with short reaction times.

To benchmark the performance of our catalyst, we attempted to prepare 3fd, derived from an aliphatic alkyne (1f) and sterically demanding aryl azide (2d), using the previously reported transition metal-free methodology (20 mol % KO^tBu in anhydrous DMSO).¹⁴ However, under these conditions only 18% of the target 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole (3fd) was formed after 18 h at room temperature, alongside many side products, including azide decomposition species.

We then investigated the methodology toward substituted aromatic azides containing fluoro- or trifluoromethyl-groups. The reaction of alkyne 1a with 1-azido-4-(trifluoromethyl)benzene (2e) gave the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole (3ae) in excellent yield (98%) after just 1 h of heating. In addition, 4-azido-2-fluoro-1-methylbenzene (2f) reacts with 1-ethynyl-4-methylbenzene (1b) to give triazole (3bf) in 83% yield, whereas 1-ethynyl-4-fluorobenzene (1h) reacts with benzylazide (2a) to give triazole (3ha) in 73% yield.

1,5-Disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles derived from aliphatic azides and alkynes bearing pendant donor atoms such as azidomethylphenylsulfane (2g) and 3-dimethylamino-1-propyne (1i) reacted smoothly to give the triazoles (3ag and 3ib) in 73% and 92% yield, respectively. This contrasts with many of the Cu-catalyzed methodologies in which molecules containing free donor atoms are known to deactivate the Cu-catalyst, although developments have been made to circumvent this issue.^{38,39} Pleasingly, this methodology also showed good compatibility with sensitive functional groups and triazoles 3jb and 3ah derived from 4-cyanophenylacetylene (1j) or 4-nitrophenylazide (2h) could be isolated in 37% (81% spectroscopic yield) and 61% yield, respectively. The low isolated yield of 3jb is attributed to difficulties associated with its purification. These functional groups are a common pitfall when using organometallic reagents and typically necessitate the use of cryogenic temperatures to mitigate side reactions. This system therefore illustrates the advantages of employing a selective s-block bimetallic reagent under catalytic conditions.

That notwithstanding, the sodium magnesiate precatalyst fails to enable the synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles derived from ethynyl-trimethylsilane or azido-trimethylsilane. This is attributed primarily to steric bulk, but other factors are likely to contribute to this lack of reactivity (see supplemental information). When the aliphatic 1-azido-adamantane (2i) was treated with 1-ethynyl-4-methylbenzene (1b) under the optimized reaction conditions, only a modest 18% yield of the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole was isolated (3bi) after extended heating (16 h). Slightly improved isolated yields (33%) were achieved using the less sterically demanding *n*-butylazide (2j) and ethynylbenzene (1a) to give the corresponding triazole (3aj), supporting the profound influence of steric factors.

Encouraged by the versatility of this method, we then explored the synthesis of symmetric and nonsymmetric di-triazoles derived from 1,4-diethynylbenzene (4a) and octa-1,7-diyne (4b) (Figure 2). The reaction of 4a with two equivalents of azide (2b or 2c), using 5 mol % of the (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄ precatalyst, gave the

Figure 2. Synthesis of symmetric and nonsymmetric di-triazoles using $(TMEDA)_2Na_2Mg(CH_2SiMe_3)_4$ pre-catalyst

^aTwo equivalents of azide used.

^bOne equivalent of azide used.

^c15% yield of symmetric di-triazole **5bdd**.

^d12% yield of symmetric di-triazole **5add**.

^eOne pot reaction.

^fOverall yield for the two-step reaction. The yield of **5adg** starting from isolated **5ad** was 94%.

corresponding di-triazoles (**5abb** and **5acc**) in high yields (83% and 81%, respectively). Using just one equivalent of azide (**5d**) with **4a** or **4b**, the desired mono- substituted triazoles (**5bd** and **5ad**) could be accessed in good yields (78% and 82%, respectively) and selectivity (15% and 12% of the di-triazoles were also produced, respectively). The nonsymmetric di-triazole (**5adg**) could be prepared via a one-pot methodology in 58% yield or 94% yield directly from isolated **5ad** (overall

Figure 3. Preparation of active catalysts

(A) Synthesis of tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiates (**6a** and **6b**).

(B) Solid-state structure of **6a**, highlighting the smallest repeating unit and different sodium coordination environments.

(C) Solid-state structure of **6b**, highlighting the smallest repeating unit and different sodium coordination environments.

yield for the two reactions is 77%). The 1,5-selectivity for the formation of triazoles and di-triazoles was confirmed by X-ray diffraction studies on **5ad** and **5adg**. Although symmetric di-triazoles have been prepared using stoichiometric Grignard¹² and zinc acetylides,¹⁵ there are limited examples where this transfers smoothly to catalytic regimes.^{14,16} Furthermore, the excellent control of reactivity and selectivity on these transformations, uncovers a new method for the synthesis of non-symmetric di-triazoles under catalytic conditions.

A series of stoichiometric studies were carried out to gain insight into the constitution of possible organometallic intermediates involved in this transformation. The addition of four equivalents of phenylacetylene (**1a**) or 1-ethynyl-4-methylbenzene (**1b**) to a THF- d_8 solution of $(\text{TMEDA})_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_4$ precatalyst indicated the 4-fold deprotonation and clean conversion through to a single species, identified as the corresponding tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate (**6a** and **6b**). Under these conditions, and the catalytic reaction conditions, the TMEDA donor is displaced by the THF- d_8 solvent. The tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiates (**6a** and **6b**) were independently prepared from $\text{NaCH}_2\text{SiMe}_3$, $\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_2$, and alkyne (**1a** or **1b**) in a 2:1:4 ratio in a combination of hexane and THF (Figure 3).

Compounds **6a** and **6b** form infinite 1-dimensional polymers in the solid-state, in which the magnesium centers are formally bonded to four acetylide fragments to give dianionic $[\text{Mg}(\text{CHC-Ar})_4]^{2-}$ units that are charge balanced with solvated sodium cations. These structures can be described as Weiss motifs.⁴⁰ The sodium cations occupy slightly different capping or bridging environments, all of which feature h^2-p -coordination to two or more acetylide CC triple bonds. The sodium coordination sphere is completed with one or two molecules of THF. Despite their intricate

Figure 4. Stoichiometric reaction between tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate (6b) and four equivalents of azide (2d), followed by an aqueous quench. The inset shows the solid-state structure of 7bd, illustrating the repeating unit of the coordination polymer.

polymeric arrangement in the solid state, compounds 6a and 6b form discrete monomeric $[\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{ChC-Ar})_4(\text{THF})_n]$ units in solution, as shown by DOSY NMR studies (see Figures S1 and S2 in the supplemental information for full details).

The tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiates are catalytically active species, and using 5 mol % of 6a, the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole (3aa) was successfully prepared from phenylacetylene (1a) and benzylazide (2a) in comparable times and yields to $(\text{TMEDA})_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_4$, supporting the hypothesis that these species may participate in the catalytic cycle. Additionally, a crossover experiment using 10 mol % of 6b to catalyze the reaction between 1-ethynylcyclohexene (1f) and 1-azido-2-methoxybenzene (2c) afforded a mixture of 3bc and 3fc in a ratio and spectroscopic yield (29% and 62%, respectively), approaching the theoretical maximum illustrating that the acetylides in the active tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate are transferred to the azide during the reaction and highlighting the necessity for initial deprotonative metalation (see Scheme S2 in the supplemental information for more details).

The next steps of the catalytic cycle were then probed by the addition of organic azides to the tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiates, 6a and 6b. Initially, 6b was treated with four equivalents of 2-azido-1,3-dimethylbenzene (2d) in THF at 65 °C for 1 h, which led to the isolation of the unexpected 4-triazenyl-1,2,3-triazole sodium complex, 7bd in 28% yield (Figure 4) (supplemental information). In the solid state, 7bd exhibits a polymeric structure, and it can be envisaged as the product of a second azide insertion into the M-C bond (M = Mg or Na) of a putative metalated triazolyl intermediate. Similar by-products have been previously proposed or observed after hydrolysis for sodium and magnesium-acetylides when an excess of azide is used in the reaction.^{11,12} When the reaction was repeated and quenched with water, GC analysis indicated that only *protio*-triazenyl-triazole (8bd) and free alkyne (1b) were formed, with no evidence of the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazole

Scheme 1. Stoichiometric reaction of tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate (6a) with one and two equivalents of azide (2c)

(3bd). Remarkably, no 8bd is formed under the standard catalytic conditions, even when two equivalents of azide are used in the reaction. Compounds 7bd and 8bd can be prepared and isolated directly from $\text{NaCH}_2\text{SiMe}_3$, 1-ethynyl-4-methylbenzene (1b) and 2-azido-1,3-dimethylbenzene (2d) (1:1:2 ratio) in a 65% and 79% yield, respectively (see supplemental information for more details). These results suggest that under stoichiometric conditions, only two of the four acetylides undergo a cyclization with 2d to give the initial triazole intermediate, which, in the absence of free alkyne to regenerate the catalyst and release the organic triazole 3bd, is instead intercepted by unreacted 2d to give 7bd. In the reaction of 6b with four equivalents of 2d, it is therefore postulated that two equivalents of 7bd are formed alongside one equivalent of the magnesium bis-acetylide $[\text{Mg}(\text{ChC}-p\text{-Tol})_2(\text{THF})_4]$ (9b) due to redistribution; however, the latter species could not be directly observed by spectroscopic methods.

To minimize this possible side reaction, the tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiates (6a or 6b) were reacted with one or two equivalents of 1-azido-2-methoxybenzene (2c) or 2-azido-1,3-dimethylbenzene (2d). The reaction of 6a with one equivalent of 2c indicated the formation of one major product (10ac) by ^1H and DOSY NMR spectroscopy (Figure S3), with a calculated molecular weight of 817 g mol^{-1} (expected = $826.36 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ - 2% error), consistent with cyclization of one of the four acetylide substituents (Scheme 1). On addition of a further equivalent of azide, the formation of two products in a 58:42 ratio was observed, as- signed respectively as the bis-triazolide (11ac) and mono-triazenyl-triazole species (12ac) resulting from the insertion of the extra equivalent of 2c in the Mg-C(imida- zoly) bond of 10ac.

Aiming to get further mechanistic insights, these stoichiometric investigations were complemented with kinetic studies on a model reaction between

Figure 5. Kinetic studies

(A) Model reaction for the cycloaddition of 1-ethynylcyclohexene (1f) and 1-azido-2-methoxybenzene (2c) and (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄ precatalyst used for kinetic studies.

(B) Plot of ln([Azide]/[Azide]₀) vs. reaction time at four different alkyne concentrations.

(C) Plot of ln([Azide]/[Azide]₀) vs. reaction time at four different precatalyst concentrations.

1-ethynylcyclohexene (1f) and 1-azido-2-methoxybenzene (2c) in the presence of (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄ precatalyst (Figure 5). The reaction mixture was heated to 40°C and periodically monitored by ¹H NMR spectroscopy. First, the effect of the azide concentration on the reaction rate was investigated by monitoring the reaction between 1f (4.14 M) and 2c (0.36 M) mediated by (TMEDA)₂Na₂Mg(CH₂SiMe₃)₄ (7.5 mol%), in which the molar ratio of alkyne to azide was 11.5:1, maintaining *pseudo*-first-order conditions. Similarly, the effect of alkyne and precatalyst concentration was studied through four sets of experiment varying the concentration of only one component while keeping the concentration of the other two components constant, and always maintaining an alkyne to azide molar ratio greater than 10:1.

The kinetic data shown in Figure S5 reveal a linear dependence of ln[Azide] on reaction time, which is consistent with a first-order dependence of the catalytic rate on azide concentration. Kinetic plots for the catalytic reaction rate as a function of alkyne concentration, ranging from 3.8 to 5.6 M (Figures 5B and S7), and precatalyst

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanism for the regioselective synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles catalyzed by $(\text{TMEDA})_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_4$

loading varying from 6.5 mol % to 9 mol % (Figures 5C and S9) indicate that the reaction is zeroth-order in alkyne and first order in catalyst. Overall, the empirical rate law is given by:

$$v = k[\text{Alkyne}]^0[\text{Azide}]^1[\text{Catalyst}]^1$$

These kinetic studies indicate that the insertion of the azide into the Mg-C bond is the rate-determining step, and perhaps more importantly, only one of the four alkynyl substituents of the tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate (6) is active at a time in the catalytic process. Based on these findings, a mechanism for the regioselective synthesis of 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles catalyzed by higher-order sodium magnesiate $(\text{TMEDA})_2\text{Na}_2\text{Mg}(\text{CH}_2\text{SiMe}_3)_4$ can be postulated (Scheme 2).

The first step involves 4-fold deprotonation of the terminal alkyne ($1x$) by the precatalyst to give the active tetra-alkynyl sodium magnesiate catalyst (6x). Reversible coordination of the azide ($2y$) to the Lewis acidic sodium cation gives intermediate $13xy$, which is then primed for the insertion of the azide in one of its Mg-C bonds forming $14xy$, which in turn can undergo fast intramolecular cyclization by the nucleophilic attack of the N atom coordinated to Mg to the CC triple bond, with the latter being activated by its p-coordination to Na giving $15xy$. It should be noted that related cyclizations facilitated by the p-coordination of an alkali-metal to an alkyne have been reported by us for the intramolecular hydroalkoxylation of alcohols catalyzed by a potassium magnesiate.³⁰ Rapid protonolysis of $15xy$ with alkyne ($1x$) will then regenerate the active catalyst (6x) and liberate the triazole product ($3xy$). This deprotonation step will also be favored by the well-established enhanced basicity of alkali-metal magnesiates,²⁷ which can be an important feature when using less activated alkyl acetylenes. This proposed mechanism, with an empirical rate law displaying a first-order dependence in catalyst and azide, would be in agreement with our kinetic studies. Underpinned by this special Na/Mg cooperative behavior, this

mechanistic proposal also supports the lack of reactivity observed when 15-crown-5 is added as an additive (Table 1, entry 9), as the preferred coordination of this macro- cyclic donor to Na would hinder the activation of the CC triple bond via Na-p interactions. However, it should also be noted that the kinetic data that we have obtained could also support an alternative mechanism for the formation of 15xy, via a classic Huisgen's concerted 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of 13xy (see Figure S10 in supplemental information).

Interestingly, despite their contrasting regioselectivities, it should be noted that this cooperative Na/Mg bimetallic mechanism bears some similarities to the one previously described by Fokin for CuAAC reactions.⁴¹ In that case, reactions are proposed to occur via the formation of a s-p-bis(copper) acetylide intermediate,⁴² to which the azide can undergo ligation and migratory insertion in a stepwise manner, forming exclusively the 1,4-substituted regioisomer. Here the large polarity of the Mg-N bond as part of a formally dianionic magnesiate, coupled with the alkyne π -coordination to the more electropositive Na atom switches on the regioselectivity of the cyclization step, enabling formation of the 1,5-substituted triazoles.

Conclusions

A versatile and efficient approach has been developed to access synthetically valuable 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles using s-block bimetallic cooperative catalysis. Complementing the isolation of potential key reaction intermediates with kinetic and spectroscopic studies, a new cooperative mechanism has been established arising from a unique combination of (1) an anionic magnesiate with enhanced nucleophilic/basic power over that of a neutral Mg complex; and (2) a built-in Lewis acid, Na, to which not only the azide but also the CC triple bond can coordinate, enabling their activation and close proximity to the reactive anionic "ate" moiety of the catalyst. This special scenario is not available for single metal systems. We believe these findings should foster new investigations on the vast untapped potential of s-block cooperative catalysis from both a preparative and mechanistic perspective.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Full experimental procedures are provided in the supplemental information.

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Eva Hevia (eva.hevia@dcb.unibe.ch).

Materials availability

All other data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article and supplemental information or from the lead contact upon reasonable request.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The X-ray crystal structure determination service unit of the Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry of the University of Bern is acknowledged for measuring, solving, refining, and summarizing the structures of compounds 3ac, 6a, 6b, and 7bd. The Synergy diffractometer was partially funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF), Switzerland within the R'Equip program (project number 206021_177033). E.H. also thanks the University of Bern and the SNF (grant number 188573) for the generous sponsorship of this research. A.H.-G. acknowledges the Comunidad de Madrid and UAH for funding through the Research Talent Attraction Program (2018-T1/AMB-11478) and Programa Estímulo a la Investigación de Jóvenes Investigadores (CM/JIN/2019-030).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M.D.T., A.M.B., A.H.-G., and E.H. conceived the project. M.D.T. carried out initial screening work. M.D.T., A.M.B., and A.H.-G. contributed to the optimization of the reaction. M.D.T., A.M.B., and A.H.-G. exemplified the scope of the reaction and carried out the mechanistic investigation. A.R.K. and A.H.-G. carried out the structural determination studies. All authors contributed to the design of the experiments. A.M.B. and E.H. wrote the manuscript, with contributions from all authors. E.H. secured the funding and directed the work.

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